

ALTERNATE	ROUTE	ATLANTIC AVE CORRIDOR ITS	ATLANTIC CITY ELECTRIC	ELECTRIC VEHICLE CHARGING INFRASTRUCTURE	VIDEO ANALYTICS CAMERAS AND PLATFORM - PHASE I	AC JITNEY	ATLANTIC CITY MUNICIPAL UTILITIES AUTHORITY	CONNECTED VEHICLE INFRASTRUCTURE - PHASE I	PACIFIC AVE CORRIDOR ITS	ARCTIC AVE CORRIDOR ITS	FREE EV CHARGING		
	TRAFFIC CONGESTION	PROJECT COST: \$2.7M		PROJECT COST: \$2.6M	PROJECT COST: \$2.2M			PROJECT COST: \$2.9M	PROJECT COST: \$3.7M	PROJECT COST: \$2.7M			
PROJECT COST: \$2.3M	TRAVELER INFORMATION	<p style="text-align: center;">Wireless World Research Forum June 18, 2024</p> <p style="text-align: center;">ATLANTIC CITY</p> <p style="text-align: center;">SMART CITY TRANSPORTATION MASTER PLAN & SAFETY ACTION PLAN</p> <p style="text-align: right; border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;">CYBERSECURITY</p> <p style="text-align: left; border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; transform: rotate(-45deg);">TRANSPORTATION MOBILITY & SAFETY</p>										VIDEO ANALYTICS CAMERAS AND PLATFORM - PHASE II	PROJECT COST: \$2.5M
	TRANSPORTATION MOBILITY & SAFETY											CONNECTED VEHICLE INFRASTRUCTURE - PHASE II	PROJECT COST: \$3.3M
	NJ TRANSIT BUS											RIDE SHARE SERVICES	
PROJECT COST: \$4.6M	EMERGENCY ROUTES ITS											TRANSPORTATION MOBILITY & SAFETY	
	ATLANTIC CITY CONVENTION CENTER											TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT CENTER (TMC) DEVELOPMENT	PROJECT COST: \$1.7M
	AV SHUTTLE SYSTEM (MAAS/MOD)											CASINOS	
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		ADVANCED TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM - PHASE I	PROJECT COST: \$1.3M										
		ATLANTIC CITY BOARDWALK											
		PEDESTRIAN AND BIKE SAFETY SYSTEM - PHASE I	PROJECT COST: \$1.3M										

Atlantic City, New Jersey

- 12 Square miles
- 38,000 residents
- Nine Casinos
- 25+ million yearly visitors
- 25,000 hospitality workers
- Multi-modal transportation
- \$3.3B net casino revenue yet, 35% of residents live below poverty level

Smart City Transportation Plan Goals

Enhanced Mobility

Improved Safety

Improved Air Quality

Reduced Congestion

ATLANTIC CITY
SMART CITY TRANSPORTATION MASTER PLAN
AUGUST 2023

Prepared for:

City of Atlantic City
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	PEDESTRIAN AND BIKE SAFETY SYSTEM - PHASE II PROJECT COST: \$1.3M		
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Safety Action Plan (SS4A) Goals

- **Safer People** - Encourage safe, responsible driving and behavior by people who use our roads and create conditions that prioritize their ability to reach their destination unharmed.
- **Safer Roads** - Design roadway environments to mitigate human mistakes and account for injury tolerances, to encourage safer behaviors, and to facilitate safe travel by the most vulnerable users.
- **Safer Vehicles** - Expand the availability of vehicle systems and features that help to prevent crashes and minimize the impact of crashes on both occupants and non-occupants.
- **Safer Speeds** - Promote safer speeds in all roadway environments through a combination of thoughtful, equitable, context-appropriate roadway design, appropriate speed-limit setting, targeted education, outreach campaigns, and enforcement.
- **Post-Crash Care** - Enhance the survivability of crashes through expedient access to emergency medical care, while creating a safe working environment for vital first responders and preventing secondary crashes through robust traffic incident management practices.

Safety Action Plan Components

Leadership Commitment and Goal Setting

Equity Considerations

Planning Structure

Policy and Process Changes

Safety Analysis

Strategy and Project Selections

Engagement and Collaboration

Progress and Transparency

Crash Analysis & Network Screening

Crash Data (2017-2021)

Total Crashes: 5,923

FSI Crashes: 75

Ped Crashes: 239

Cyclist Crashes: 88

- Crashes
- Commuting Patterns
- Community Profile
- Congestion

Crash Analysis & Network Screening

Fatal & Serious Injury Crashes by Type (2017 - 2021)

- Crashes
- Commuting Patterns
- Community Profile
- Congestion

Crash Analysis & Network Screening

Pedestrian & Bike Crash Apparent Contributing Circumstances

- Crashes
- Commuting Patterns
- Community Profile
- Congestion

Commuting Patterns

JOURNEY TO WORK DATA

Drive Alone

Transit

Walk

Bike

	Drive Alone	Transit	Walk	Bike
Atlantic City	45%	20%	18%	1%
Atlantic County	70%	4%	4%	<1%
New Jersey	62%	8%	3%	<1%

32% of workers age 16+ in Atlantic City do not have a vehicle

- Crashes
- Commuting Patterns
- Community Profile
- Congestion

Source: American Community Survey 5-Year Data (2021)

Commuting Patterns

JOURNEY TO WORK DATA

Drive Alone

45%

Transit

20%

Walk

18%

Bike

1%

**Atlantic
City**

- Seven NJ TRANSIT bus routes (Routes 501, 502, 504, 505, 507, 508, 509)
- NJ Transit Atlantic City Rail Line
- Jitneys (Shuttle Buses)

- Crashes
- Commuting Patterns
- Community Profile
- Congestion

Community Profile & Equity Considerations

- Crashes
- Commuting Patterns
- Community Profile
- Congestion

SOCIOECONOMIC FACTORS	ATLANTIC CITY	ATLANTIC COUNTY	NEW JERSEY
Minority	78.8%	39.0%	39.3%
Low-Income	32.9%	14.8%	11.2%
Limited English-Speaking Households	25.8%	15.4%	7.1%
Under the age of 5	6.6%	4.9%	5.5%
Between 5 & 17	16.9%	15.8%	16.0%
Over 65	16.9%	28.1%	17.4%
Does Not Own a Car	31.0%	9.7%	10.9%
Less than High School Education	25.6%	10.3%	12.6%
Unemployment	13.1%	6.4%	5.0%

Source: U.S. Census American Community Survey (ACS) 5-Year Estimates (2018-2022)

Congestion

Traffic Volumes, Travel Time, Delays

- Generally balanced traffic flows during peak hours
- PM Peak Hour highest of the three peak periods
- Dynamic conditions, such as major concerts or events at the beach

- Crashes
- Commuting Patterns
- Community Profile
- Congestion

Smart City Transportation Public Engagement

- Public Involvement Action Plan (PIAP)
- Project Website www.ACITSMasterPlan.com
- Stakeholder Meetings – April & May 2023
- Public Information Center – June 2023

Public Involvement Action Plan (PIAP)

Pacific Avenue Signal Optimization Project
Smart City Transportation Master Plan
City of Atlantic City
Atlantic County, NJ

City of Atlantic City

Pacific Avenue Signal Optimization
Hartford Avenue to Massachusetts Avenue

Tuesday June 20, 2023

6 PM - 8 PM

PUBLIC INFORMATION CENTER

Carnegie Center
35 South Martin Luther King Boulevard
2nd Floor Lecture Room
Atlantic City, NJ 08401

Atlantic City will be hosting a Public Information Center (PIC) to inform local residents, officials, businesses, and the general public about the deployment of an advanced traffic signal system project along the Pacific Avenue corridor from Hartford Avenue to Massachusetts Avenue. The purpose of this Public Information Center is to share information on the project and solicit input on the traffic signal timing improvements.

This project is being funded using Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) Congestion Mitigation and Air Quality Improvement Program (CMAQ) funds made available through the South Jersey Transportation Planning Organization (SJTPO).

FOR MORE INFO VISIT
www.ACITSMasterPlan.com

Safety Action Plan (SS4A) Public Engagement

- Public Outreach Plan (POP)
- Project Website & Surveys www.RoadSafetyAC.com
- Steering Advisory Committee & Stakeholder Meetings – March 2024
- Public Information Center – April 2024

ITS Architecture

Systems Engineering Review Form
Programmatic ITS
May 2023

Pacific Avenue from MP 0.00 to MP 2.51
City of Atlantic City – Pacific Avenue Signal System
City of Atlantic City
Atlantic County, New Jersey

- Identification of portions of the ITS architecture being implemented:**
The New Jersey Statewide ITS Architecture serves as the framework for the development of the project architecture.
Market Package(s):
ATMS01 Network Surveillance
ATMS03 Surface Street Control
Subsystem(s):
ROADWAY SUBSYSTEM
TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT
Architecture Flow:
CITY FIELD EQUIPMENT ↔ CITY TRAFFIC OPERATIONS CENTER → CITY POLICE / NJ TRANSIT / SJTA / TRAFFIC OPERATIONS CENTER SOUTH / ARTERIAL MANAGEMENT CENTER
- Identification of participating agencies roles and responsibilities (Concepts of Operation):**
Atlantic City will be the lead agency for overseeing the design and construction for the project. Atlantic City will also be the lead agency responsible for operations and maintenance. Atlantic City will share the ITS information with TRANSCOM, NJ Transit, Police, SJTA, other regional transportation authorities, local traffic management, and emergency response services. The appropriate level of information is shared with the public through NJDOT's SWIFT program through both web and phone based systems.
- Requirements Definitions:**
High-Level
 - The system shall provide surveillance coverage.
 - The system shall provide automated intersection traffic presence monitoring.
 - The system shall provide automated traffic signal timing control adjustments in response to traffic presence monitoring.

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NJDOT SERF

NJ & National ITS Architecture was used as a framework to plan, define, and integrate ITS technologies for interoperability

Fiber Optic Communications

Existing & Planned Fiber Network

Smart City Transportation Plan Project Prioritization

Project Name	Estimated Cost (\$mil)	Term
Tier 1		
Evacuation Routes ITS	\$4.6	Short
Traveler Information	\$2.3	Short
Atlantic Ave Corridor ITS	\$2.7	Short
Electric Vehicle Charging Infrastructure	\$2.6	Short
Video Analytics Cameras and Platform – Phase I	\$2.2	Short
Connected Vehicle Infrastructure – Phase I	\$2.9	Short
Pacific Ave Corridor ITS	\$3.7	Short
Arctic Ave Corridor ITS	\$2.7	Medium
Video Analytics Cameras and Platform – Phase II	\$2.5	Medium
Connected Vehicle Infrastructure – Phase II	\$3.3	Medium
Tier 2		
Traffic Management Center (TMC) Development	\$1.7	Short
Pedestrian and Bike Safety System - Phase I	\$1.3	Short
Advanced Traffic Management System – Phase I	\$1.3	Short
Transit Signal Priority/Emergency Vehicle Preemption	\$2.9	Medium
Advanced Traffic Management System – Phase II	\$3.3	Medium
Pedestrian and Bike Safety System - Phase II	\$1.3	Medium
Tier 3		
AV Shuttle System (MaaS/MoD)	\$5.2	Long

- Short (1-3 years)
- Medium (3-8 years)
- Long (8+ years)

Tier 1

These are technologies that have reached maturity, possess a short implementation timeline, and exhibit cost-efficiency. Most of these technologies focus on spot-level improvements.

Tier 2

These technologies are mostly mature and require active preparation within the next five years. These technologies usually require systematic upgrade.

Tier 3

Although not yet mature, these technologies promise to bring multiple benefits to the city.

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Video Analytics

- ACPD deploying 200 multi-sensor CCTV cameras
- Machine-learning AI video analytics that include ITS functionality
- Can be leveraged with future Advanced Traffic Management System (ATMS) Software and Traffic Camera deployment

ACHILES

Atlantic City Headquarters for Intelligence Logistics Electronic Surveillance

- Genetec Security Center
- Traffic Monitoring capabilities

Operational Technology (OT) Cybersecurity Considerations

- Executive Order 14028, dated May 12th, 2021, explicitly includes requirements for OT Cybersecurity Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA) design, incident response plans, continuous monitoring, and other OT specific controls.
- ISA/IEC 62443 series of standards must be referenced to ensure all ITS is designed in accordance with Industrial Automation Control System requirements.
- NIST SP 800-82r3, Guide to OT Security, must be referenced as well with respect to ITS cybersecurity design requirements and best practices.
- Consequence-driven, Cyber-informed Engineering (CCE) methodology ensures OT cybersecurity is included as part of a full system lifecycle.

Consequence-driven Cyber-informed Engineering (CCE)

Source: DOE Idaho National Laboratory CCE Program for OT Cybersecurity

Maintenance & Operations

- Asset Management
 - GIS based inventory
 - Digital twin
- Establish Maintenance Program
 - Preventive
 - Routine
 - Emergency Repair
- Staff Training
 - Software & equipment maint. & ops

Performance Measures & Big Data

Measures of Effectiveness (MOEs) & Automated Traffic Signal Performance Measures (ATSPMs)

- Travel Time
- Queue Length
- Vehicle Delay
- Number of stops
- Crash Data
- Stakeholder/Public Complaints
- Equipment & Software Health

Smart Traffic Signals Concept Design

Pacific Avenue: 2.51 miles – 36 signals
 Atlantic Avenue: 3.27 miles – 47 signals
 Arctic Avenue: 1.66 miles – 35 signals

Pacific Avenue Corridor Smart Signals

Project limits:

- 35 existing signalized intersections on Pacific Avenue from Albany Avenue to New Hampshire Avenue
- Fiber connection to City Hall along Tennessee Avenue and connection to Public Safety Building along Iowa Avenue

Smart City Transportation Master Plan Implementation Options

- **Pilot Projects**

- Test at select intersections
 - + *Reduced installation costs and required staff time.*
 - *Limited locations with available performance measures.*

- **Integrated Upgrades**

- Upgrade as part of other projects.
 - + *Limited upfront investment and ability to conduct thorough gap assessment.*
 - *Upgraded equipment may be inconsistent.*

- **System-wide Implementation**

- Deploy at all intersections.
 - + *Ability to track performance measures across the system.*
 - *Increased installation costs and required staff time.*

Implementation & Next Steps

Pacific Avenue Project

Activity	Timeframe
Pacific Avenue Final Design	Fall 2023 to Spring 2024
Anticipated Federal Authorization for Construction	Summer 2024
Anticipated Construction Start	Late 2024
Construction Complete	Late 2025

City-Wide Projects

Activity	Timeframe
Atlantic Avenue Road Multi-Modal Safety Improvements Construction	Sept 2024
ACPD CCTV Cameras	Fall 2024
Grant Applications SS4A, SMART, HSIP etc.	2024+

Lessons Learned

Case Study – Smart Columbus, Ohio

The Smart Columbus Program was funded primarily by the \$40M USDOT Smart City Challenge (SCC). USDOT sought to “demonstrate how advanced data and intelligent transportation systems (ITS) technologies and applications can be used to reduce congestion, keep travelers safe, protect the environment, respond to climate change, connect underserved communities, and support economic vitality.” The funding was used to execute demonstration projects designed to create a more connected, safer and sustainable city that included:

- Smart Columbus Operating System
- Connected Vehicle Environment
- Multimodal Trip Planning Application
- Mobility Assistance for People with Cognitive Disabilities
- Prenatal Trip Assistance
- Smart Mobility Hubs
- Event Parking Management
- Connected Electric Autonomous Vehicles

Case Study – Smart Columbus

TECHNOLOGY ELEMENTS

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO URBAN TRANSPORTATION ELEMENTS

SMART CITY ELEMENTS

Linden LEAP (Linden Empowers All People) Driverless Shuttle

Connected Electric Autonomous Vehicles (CEAV) deployments through the Smart City Challenge (SCC) program

COST

GENERAL DEVELOPMENT
\$400K

SMART CIRCUIT
\$500K
 (ODOT only)

LINDEN LEAP
\$2.3M

DEMONSTRATION

GENERAL DEVELOPMENT
 September 2016 to March 2018

SMART CIRCUIT
 December 2018 to December 2019

LINDEN LEAP
 February 2020 to March 2021

PEOPLE SERVED

SMART CIRCUIT

- **16,062** passengers
- **19,118** miles traveled

LINDEN LEAP

- **3,598** food boxes distributed
- **15,260** masks distributed
- **12** local operators hired

INFRASTRUCTURE

SCIOTO MILE

- **6** shuttles
- **4** stops

LINDEN LEAP

- **2** shuttles
- **4** stops

OUTCOMES

MOBILITY

- Over 800 miles traveled
- 265 walkup visits

OPPORTUNITY

- More than 130,000 meals

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

- Over 90% of patrons very satisfied

Linden LEAP Passenger Service Route Map

SUSTAINABILITY

Use of the Connected Electric Autonomous Vehicles in Linden concluded in April 2020, but the City will continue the food pantry service delivery to Rosewind using a traditional vehicle. The project lessons learned and deployment playbook will also be published to transfer knowledge to other agencies.

Linden LEAP (Linden Empowers All People) Driverless Shuttle

- Since 2016, the **Smart Columbus** program has been helping the City respond to its residents needs via innovative technology
- **Connected Electric Autonomous Vehicles (CEAV)**, aka self-driving shuttles, are an important part of the Smart Columbus portfolio
- The **Linden LEAP** (Linden Empowers All People) Shuttle, a connected electric autonomous vehicle launched in February 2020
- When COVID-19 impacted its ability to provide passenger service, Columbus **reimagined the mission** of the CEAV, launching a **food pantry delivery** service
- The service **distributed 3,598 food pantry boxes**, equivalent to almost 130,000 meals

The Linden LEAP Shuttle demonstrated how autonomous vehicles can be used to **improve equity and accessibility** in underserved neighborhoods.

Linden LEAP (Linden Empowers All People) Driverless Shuttle

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Smart Columbus Lessons Learned

- **Adaptability**
 - Be prepared to change course as technology evolves
- **User-Centric Approach**
 - Prioritize user needs and strategic outcomes
- **Robust Program Management Office (PMO)**
 - A dedicated team ensures efficient program delivery
- **Collaboration**
 - Partner across sectors for impactful outcomes
- **Data Privacy and Agile Systems Engineering**
 - Embrace new practices for success
- **Holistic Portfolio Management**
 - Align goals and solutions
- **Preparedness for Challenges**
 - Adapt to external forces

Wireless World Research Forum - June 18, 2024

Brad Miller, PE, PP, PTOE
Associate Vice President
Dept. Manager ITS & Traffic
Engineering
Michael Baker International

THANK YOU!